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INTERVIEW QUESTIONS

Explain the Reasons to Emigrate:

Explain the Reasons for your emigration

May you tell about your migratory trajectory in the different dimensions:

- 1) The professional field
- 2) Professional trajectory? Obstacles/opportunities?
- 3) Sentimental trajectory, family project
- 4) Problems isolation, loneliness, mental health, immigration problem

What is your relationship with your country of origin?

Personal relationships at origin and destination?

May we reflect together on the identity of migrant women in transformation?

The evolution you have lived through, the spaces where women find themselves?

SECOND PART

What are your reasons to approach writing, poetry, literature?

Why do you write? Starting writing?

What is reflected of your migratory experience in your works?

How much of your life is reflected in your novels?

What is the message you want to give to society?

What is the message you want to give to the political world?

How can literature contribute to raise awareness?

What is the mission of writing, life-writing, in your opinion?

From your point of view, what is the impact that your work has and has had on society?

Is there some feedback from your audience that you would like to share?

How do you help to transmit the memory of your generation, your origin, and your people?

What is the place of memory?

Has writing changed your life in any way?

How has writing changed your inner world?

How has writing changed your external world? Your environment? Do your eyes see it differently?

What is the power of writing for you?

Have you use writing with a transformative meaning?

Does writing have a transformative power? Is it a transformative tool?

Is your writing self-reflective? Does it speak of yourself and your migration experience?

What language do you write in?

How do you use different languages in your writing?

Could you give an example of the workshops you run?

May you share your METHODOLOGY?